

A Rapid Spectrophotometric Method for Trace Determination of Copper in Milk

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Copper(II) interacts with 4-(2-quinolyazo)phenol (*p*-QAP) to give a violet coloured (1 : 3) complex soluble in ethanolic medium. The complex exhibits maximum absorbance at 535 nm in the pH range 8.0-11.1. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.0008 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ ($\epsilon=8.3 \times 10^4$). The reagent has been found to be fairly selective for the determination of copper(II) in presence of various interfering metal ions. The method has been used for the selective determination of copper in various milk samples.

COPPER is one of the important trace metals found in biological materials. Its presence in milk in excessive amount is objectionable or sometimes indicative of contamination and causes loss of ascorbic acid content. The oxidized flavour of milk has also been correlated to the presence of naturally occurring copper in it¹. Hence, the determination of copper in milk is of vital importance during processing and minimization of naturally occurring copper.

Copper has been determined spectrophotometrically in milk by different chromogenic reagents¹⁻⁵. The general disadvantage of these methods is the time-consuming extraction procedure. Besides, most of the reagents give colour reactions with iron which is also present in milk. Therefore, a method to determine copper selectively in presence of iron will be of general importance.

The present communication reports the analytical potentiality of 4-(2-quinolyazo)phenol (*p*-QAP) (I), a new heterocyclic azo dye, in the selective and sensitive determination of copper in 40% ethanolic medium. *p*-QAP does not give colour reactions with either iron(II) or iron(III). Moreover, the coloured complexes of other transition metal ions are unstable in 40% ethanolic medium. The method presented here is simple, rapid and the sensitivity is $0.0008 \mu\text{g Cu}/\text{cm}^2$ for an absorbance of 0.001.

Experimental

Apparatus : An Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer with 10 mm glass cells was used for absor-

bance measurements and a Beckman pH meter model Expandomatic SS-2 with glass electrode in conjunction with calomel electrode was used for pH measurements.

Reagents : *p*-QAP was prepared by the method of Barua *et al*⁶. A $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving 0.249 g/l of ethanol. The solution is stable for several days. Stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of AnalaR $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double distilled water containing a few drops of H_2SO_4 and was standardized by conventional methods. $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{HCl}$ acid buffer solution of pH 8.2 was used. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Milk samples : Fresh samples of cow, goat, buffalo and camel milk were procured from Bawana village, Delhi. Other milk samples were collected from milk booths and milkmen of the University area.

Recommended procedure : 1.0 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ *p*-QAP solution and 1.0 ml of buffer solution are added to a suitable aliquot containing 0.9 to 7.1 μg of copper(II). The mixture is diluted to 10.0 ml keeping ethanol concentration 40%. (Addition of 1.0 ml $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{HCl}$ solution of pH 8.2 raises the pH to 9.1 in 40% ethanol). The ethanolic mixture is heated in the water bath for ~ 5 min. The absorbance is recorded at 535 nm against a corresponding reagent blank. The concentration of copper(II) is determined from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Determination of copper in milk : The copper content of milk has been determined by the conventional dry ashing procedure⁵. 25.0 ml of milk is pipetted into a heated crucible to evaporate without frothing. After the moisture has been

removed the residue is heated strongly to 450-500°, cooled, 1.0 ml of concentrated nitric acid is added, evaporated to dryness and ignited again at 450-500° for about 1 hr. Utmost care should be taken to avoid loss by sputtering. The resulting white ash is dissolved in minimum volume of dilute nitric acid and the volume is made up to 25 ml in a volumetric flask. 1-2 ml of the solution is pipetted out, the excess nitric acid is neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and the copper content is determined following the recommended procedure.

Results and Discussion

Addition of ethanolic solution of *p*-QAP to a very dilute aqueous solution of copper(II) forms a violet coloured complex. The complex precipitates out when the ethanol concentration is less than 30% (v/v). Subsequent studies, therefore, were carried out in 40% (v/v) ethanolic medium. In this condition the complex is stable for more than 48 hr.

Spectral characteristics of Cu(II)-*p*-QAP complex : A series of solutions containing copper(II) ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) and the reagent ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) at different pH were prepared, keeping the ethanolic concentration at 40% (v/v). Their spectra were measured against respective reagent blanks. The studies reveal that only one complex, with maximum absorbance at 535 nm, is formed.

Effect of pH : The complex exhibited constant and maximum absorbance in the pH range of 8.0-11.1. It was found that addition of 1.0 ml of a solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 - \text{HCl}$ buffer of pH 8.2 was sufficient to raise the pH to 9.1 of the 40% (v/v) ethanolic solution.

Effect of time and temperature : It was observed that ~45 min are needed for full colour development at ordinary temperature. When heated on the water bath full colour developed within 5 min. The loss of volume while heating was compensated by adding ethanol. The colour did not fade at least for 48 hr after cooling to room temperature.

Effect of reagent concentration : Absorbance data measured for a series of solutions containing copper(II) ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) and varying amounts of the reagent (at pH ~9.1) showed that 5 times molar excess of *p*-QAP was required for full colour development.

Other physico-chemical characteristics : Validity of Beer's law and optimum range for accurate determination of copper(II) ions at pH 8.0-11.1, determined by Ringbom plots, are 0-0.87 ppm and 0.09-0.71 ppm, respectively. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction calculated from Beer's law plots comes out to $0.0008 \mu\text{g Cu/cm}^2$ ($\xi = 8.3 \times 10^4 \text{ l mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) for the complex at 535 nm.

Composition of the complex : The composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variation and mole ratio plots. Results obtained showed that the metal ion and the reagent interact in the ratio of 1 : 3.

Absorbance deviations : With the particular conditions adopted, the mean absorbance of ten solutions containing 1 ml of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ copper(II) was found to be 0.83, with a standard deviation of ± 0.005 for the complex.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of foreign ions was studied by adding different amount of foreign ions to be investigated to $0.635 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper(II) and determining the copper, following the recommended procedure. It has been found that F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SCN^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} , oxalate, tartrate, citrate and acetate did not interfere and so did Mg(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Sr(II), Al(III), Ga(III), In(III), Cr(III), La(III), V(V), UO₂(II), Mn(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI). (The hydroxides of some of these polyvalent metal ions can be centrifuged). The amounts of other ions (in ppm) which did not cause a deviation of more than $\pm 2.5\%$ in absorbance are given below. The complexes of Ni(II), Co(II), Hg(II) and Au(III) decompose (on standing and rapidly on heating) in 40% alcohol. The tolerance limits of these metals are 20, 10, 4 and 4, respectively. The tolerance limits of other ions are Zn(II) (20), Cd(II) (20), Pb(II) (100), Fe(III) (5 or 40 ppm masked by F^-), Os(VIII) (20, masked by NO_2^-) and Pd(II) (10, masked by SCN^-).

S^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, thiourea, CN^- and EDTA interfere seriously.

Recovery of copper in milk : The additions procedures in the milk samples were tried by adding 0.16 and 0.32 ppm of copper(II), respectively. The recovery results confirmed the precision of the method (Table 1). It has also been found that the amount of copper in different milk samples procured from milkmen and milk booths are higher than the amounts present in fresh milk samples. This fact may be attributed to the contamination of the element during processings.

Conclusion : Dithiazone, dithiocarbamates, cuproine and its analogues have been used in the spectrophotometric determination of copper. The primary disadvantages with these methods are the time-consuming extraction steps. In the dithiazone method the noble metals (Pt, Pd, Au, Ag, Hg) interfere and these metals have to be removed beforehand. The dithiocarbamate method is made selective by masking different transition and base metals with EDTA. The method, however, is not sensitive. The methods using cuproine and its analogues are specific for copper, but are of relatively low sensitivity⁷. Several other methods for sensitive determination of copper are based on azo reagents such as PAN, PAR, TAM, etc. But again these reagents form coloured complexes with many other metal ions and selectivity for copper can be achieved only after careful masking of these metal ions. The present method is direct and rapid and the complex is highly stable. The reagent is found to be highly sensitive as well as selective as most of the cations form unstable complexes under the conditions recommended. The consistency of the

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF Cu(II) IN VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	No. of sample	*Natural Cu X ppm	Total Cu (with extraneous addition of Cu)			
			Present (X+0.160) ppm	Found ppm	Present (X+0.320) ppm	Found ppm
Cow milk	1	0.212	0.372	0.375	0.532	0.537
	2	0.200	0.360	0.364	0.520	0.522
	3	0.223	0.383	0.380	0.543	0.536
	4	0.232	0.392	0.390	0.552	0.552
Buffalo milk	1	0.192	0.352	0.355	0.512	0.510
	2	0.218	0.378	0.380	0.538	0.540
	3	0.208	0.368	0.367	0.523	0.522
	4	0.198	0.358	0.360	0.518	0.522
Goat milk	1	0.088	0.248	0.246	0.408	0.410
	2	0.105	0.265	0.264	0.425	0.420
	3	0.078	0.238	0.238	0.398	0.400
Camel milk	1	0.121	0.281	0.284	0.441	0.440
	2	0.133	0.293	0.289	0.453	0.457
Milk from Govt. supply and milkmen	1	0.253	0.413	0.410	0.573	0.570
	2	0.235	0.395	0.401	0.554	0.559
	3	0.258	0.418	0.420	0.578	0.584
	4	0.219	0.379	0.382	0.539	0.530
	5	0.260	0.420	0.425	0.580	0.579

* Average of 4 readings.

TABLE 2—SENSITIVITIES OF SOME METHODS FOR DETERMINATION OF COPPER

Reagents	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g Cu/cm}^2$ for $\log I_0/I=0.001$)	Reference
Dithiazone/ CCl_4	0.0014/550 nm	7
Diethyldithiocarbamate/ CCl_4	0.0045/546 nm	7
2, 2'-Biquinoly/Isosamyl alcohol (cuproine)	0.0993/546 nm 0.0012/353 nm	7
2, 9-Dimethyl-4,7-diphenyl- 1,10-phenanthroline (Bathocuproine)/isocamyl alcohol	0.0447/479 nm 0.0029/564 nm	7 8
1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2- naphthol (PAN)/ CHCl_3	0.0014/580 nm	
4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR)	0.0052/522 nm 0.0011/510 nm	8
2-(2-Pyridylazo)- <i>p</i> -cresol/ CHCl_3	0.0023/600 nm 0.0053/740 nm	9
4-(4-Methyl-2-thiazolylazo) resorcinol	0.0028/560 nm 0.0023/520-30 nm	9
1-(2-Thiazolylazo)-5- dimethylaminophenol (TAM)	0.0016/570 nm	7
4-(2-Quinolylazo)phenol	0.0008/535 nm	Present method

results in the determination of copper level in different milk samples confirms the precision of the method. The sensitivity of the colour reaction is compared with those of some other well known reagents for copper (Table 2).

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